

Shetland port & supply chain capabilities

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report identifies and scores 20 port facilities in Shetland, ranging from small rural piers to large-scale industrial quays, and introduces the local supply chain capabilities relevant to offshore wind project support.

A scoring mechanism was developed which divided the 20 port facilities into 3 categories: Tier 1 facilities are the largest and most suitable for supporting offshore wind developments; Tier 2 facilities may have some utility for smaller scale component handling (e.g. shipping containers), vessel services or crew changes; Tier 3 facilities are thought unlikely to have utility in supporting offshore wind developments.

The Tier 1 facilities are located in Lerwick, the capital town of Shetland. They are owned and operated by the Lerwick Port Authority. The facility that ranks highest in the screening is Greenhead Base, which hosts 785m of quay and water depths down to -9m Chart Datum (CD). Dales Voe ranks second in the screening. Dales Voe is one of the strongest quaysides in Europe, with load-bearing capacity of 60Te/m², and water depths down to -12.5m CD.

Known future developments are set out which identify the plans for the large-scale build-out of the ultra-deep-water-quay (UDWQ) at Dales Voe. The first phase of this development will add 101m of heavy-duty quay, 56,000m² of additional laydown, and deepen the quay to -21m CD alongside. Subsequent development phases of the UDWQ are then described.

Plans to rework the buildings at Greenhead Base are described, representing an improvement in the site's capacity to host the assembly of floating substructures, and subsequent O&M support services.

Large-structure load in/out capabilities are summarised, identifying Dales Voe and Greenhead Base as the most suitable sites to host this activity. Previous large-structure handling experience is described, and a concise example load-in / assembly methodology for offshore wind is outlined, which includes suggestions for site setup / civil works at Greenhead Base.

Laydown and Open Storage graphics are then presented, again identifying Greenhead Base (154,000m²) and Dales Voe (37,000m²) as the leading facilities.

Wet Storage and Marshalling looks at 5 prospective areas, with areas in North Lerwick, South Lerwick representing the most attractive options, with more investigation required in the potential presented by South-East Yell. Turbine integration site analysis identifies Dales Voe as being the

only viable option if this work is to be undertaken while the substructure is moored (i.e. rather than integration taking place offshore).

Other infrastructure considerations are briefly outlined, including fuel availability, water, power, and hotel accommodation.

A local supply chain ambition statement is outlined, with a case study which details the Norn Engineering Alliance approach to supply chain collaboration, followed by a directory of relevant Shetland-based businesses.

A separate package of appendices has been collated which contains additional relevant information.

Figure 1: Greenhead Base, Lerwick (Credit: LPA / John Coutts)

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this report is to concisely set out information on Shetland’s port and supply chain capabilities in relation to future floating offshore wind projects in the region. The information presented has been collated from a variety of relevant stakeholders and is intended to provide initial information to the developer, prospective partners, and suppliers to ESB’s Stoura project. The Stoura Offshore Wind Farm project is in early-stage development approximately 40km off the East coast of Shetland (Figure 1), spanning over 100km² and set to produce 500MW of clean electricity.

Figure 2 Stoura Wind Farm location map (Credit: ESB)

Shetland is a North Atlantic archipelago made up of over 100 islands, with a total population of around 22,000. The islands are located 110 miles North of the UK mainland, and 140 miles West of Norway. Shetland has played host to nationally significant energy infrastructure developments for over 50 years and acted as a supply base throughout the development of the North Sea Oil & Gas industry. This has resulted in mature engineering supply chains and large-scale port and project infrastructure that belie the islands’ small population. All told, the Shetland energy supply chain directly employs over 1,000 Shetland-based personnel.

The Shetland supply chain are increasingly experienced in supporting the renewables sector, with the UK’s largest onshore wind farm (by output) – the 443MW Viking wind farm – due to start generating this year (2024). The islands have also played host to the world’s first tidal array in Bluemull Sound, and a number of local and community-owned windfarms, including the Burradale wind farm North of Lerwick, and the Garth wind farm in the north of Yell.

Shetland is actively engaging in the transition from traditional oil and gas industries to emerging energy sectors, with a focus on long-term sustainability and economic benefit. The region is supporting the decommissioning of North Sea oil and gas infrastructure while simultaneously planning for the development of offshore wind energy and onshore hydrogen production facilities in the region.

This strategic shift is being facilitated by the collaborative efforts across local organisations, including (but not limited to) the Shetland Net Zero Energy Forum, the 4Shetland Group, and the Energy Skills working group. These entities will be instrumental in orchestrating a coordinated transition plan, aligning with the objectives of larger bodies such as the Shetland Islands Council and the Lerwick Port Authority. The collective aim of these groups and the wider community is to ensure a structured transition, optimising the value that can be realised for the community, and contributing to the region's economic diversification and environmental sustainability.

SHETLAND PORT FACILITIES

Twenty Shetland port facilities have been assessed for suitability and ranked into three Tiers, defined in Table 1.

	Description
Tier 1	Most suitable for large-scale project support services and future O&M support hubs.
Tier 2	May have some utility for large-scale project support as locations for smaller equipment delivery, vessel servicing, O&M or crew changes.
Tier 3	Not believed to currently have the characteristics required to support an offshore wind development project, without expansion of the facility.

Table 1: Tier ranking definitions

Figure 3: Shetland port facility screening

Scoring Methodology

The assessment criteria which were used to screen the twenty identified port facilities is set out in Table 2 (below).

Distance from Stoura (km)	Quayside Water Depth (m)	Berthage (m)	Load capacity (Te/m ²)	Open storage area (m ²)	Large offshore wind project suitability	Score
<50	10+	>1,000	>45	>50,000	Experience of handling large project structures (e.g. heavy / bulky items >10,000Te across the quay) Large vessel pilotage, tugs and shoreside riggers, plant and operatives available. Large-project equipment on site or available to mobilise (e.g. heavy-duty pads, harbour cranes)	1
50 to <100	8 to <10	750 to <1,000	30 to <45	25,000 to <50,000	Pilotage available. Can facilitate general cargo handling using large mobile cranes (e.g. landing containerised equipment). Can receive project equipment (such as cranes), but not suitable for large component handling.	2
100 to <150	6 to <8	500 to <750	15 to <30	5,000 to <25,000	Suitable for the provision of project vessel services (e.g. crew changes, stores, fuel, water, etc), but limited utility for the handling of any project equipment or components.	3
>150	<6	<500	<15	<5,000	Basic facilities available for small-to-medium vessels, but extremely limited utility for project execution activities.	4

Table 2: Port facility scoring criteria

Scoring Results

The scoring results for the screened facilities are set out in Table 3 (below):

	Facility Name	Distance from Stoura (km)	Quayside Water Depth (m)	Berthage (m)	Load Capacity (Te/m ²)	Open storage area (m ²)	Large project suitability	Total Score
Tier 1	Greenhead Base	2	2	2	2	1	1	10
	Dales Voe	2	1	4	1	1	1	11
Tier 2	Holmsgarth & Mair's	2	1	1	4	1	2	13
	Scalloway	4	3	2	4	3	2	18
	Sullom Voe	2	2	4	3	2	2	16
	Cullivoe	2	3	4	4	1	3	19
Tier 3	Sella Ness	2	3	4	4	4	4	21
	Collafirth	2	3	4	4	4	4	21
	Toft	2	4	4	4	4	4	22
	Hamnavoe	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
	Walls	4	4	4	4	4	4	23
	West Burrafirth	4	3	4	4	4	4	24
	Mid Yell	2	4	4	4	4	4	22
	Baltasound	2	4	4	4	4	4	22
	Uyeasound	2	4	4	4	4	4	22
	Hamars Ness	2	4	4	4	4	4	22
	Symbister	2	3	4	4	4	3	20
	Out Skerries	1	4	4	4	4	4	21
	Fair Isle	3	4	4	4	4	4	23
	Broonie's Taing	Derelict facility						

Table 3: Port facility scoring results

Shetland Port Facility Data Table

The data that was used to rank the facilities is set out in Table 4 (below). Please note that specific load bearing capacities are not available for the facilities owned by the Shetland Islands Council (SIC). This is denoted with an asterisk (*). Load bearing requirements and capabilities can be assessed by SIC port engineers by specific request.

Facility Name	Location / (Owner)	Distance from Stoura (km)	Quayside Water Depth (m)	Berthage (m)	Load Capacity (te/m ²)	Open storage (m ²)	Tidal Conditions	
							MHWS (+m)	MLWS (+m)
Greenhead Base	Lerwick (LPA)	70	6.0 to 9.1	783	5 to 33+	160,000	2.2	0.5
Dales Voe	Lerwick (LPA)	70	9.4 to 12.5	127	60	50,000	2.2	0.5
Holmsgarth & Mair's	Lerwick (LPA)	70	5.2 to 12.5	1,727	10	21,800	2.2	0.5
Scalloway	Central Mainland (SIC)	160	3.5 to 7.0	883	1 to 5+	8,400	1.6	0.5
Sullom Voe Const. Jetty	N Mainland (SIC)	80	4.5 to 9.5	85	Max 20*	13,000	2.3	0.4
Cullivoe	Yell (SIC)	60	Up to 6.0	250	Assessment on request*	17,000	2.6	0.5
Sella Ness (Tug Jetty)	N Mainland (SIC)	80	Min 6.9	350	Assessment on request*	0	2.3	0.4
Collafirth	N Mainland (SIC)	75	5.0 to 6.0	100	Assessment on request*	1,400	2.3	0.4
Toft	N Mainland (SIC)	65	5.4 to 5.5	121	Assessment on request*	1100	2.1	0.4
Hamnavoe	Central Mainland (SIC)	160	3.4	75	Assessment on request*	0	0.5	0.0
Walls	W Mainland (SIC)	170	3.0 to 7.0	174	Assessment on request*	250	2.0	0.5
West Burrafirth	W Mainland (SIC)	200	2.5 to 5.0	100	Assessment on request*	900	2.2	0.6
Mid Yell	Yell (SIC)	60	1.5 to 2.4	90	Assessment on request*	400	2.4	0.6
Baltasound	Unst (SIC)	55	5.0	160	Assessment on request*	1,500	2.4	0.5
Uyeasound	Unst (SIC)	50	3.5 to 4.0	230	Assessment on request*	1,000	2.6	0.5
Hamars Ness	Fetlar (SIC)	50	1.9 to 4.0	40	Assessment on request*	3,500	2.4	0.4
Symbister	Whalsay (SIC)	60	5.0 to 6.0	450	Assessment on request*	1,500	2.1	0.3
Out Skerries	Out Skerries (SIC)	40	5.0	45	Assessment on request*	600	2.2	0.4
Fair Isle	Fair Isle (SIC)	140	3.58	80	Assessment on request*	0	2.2	0.6
Broonie's Taig	S Mainland (Private)	Derelict facility						

Table 4: Port facility data table

For enquiries regarding any of the Lerwick Port Authority (LPA) owned facilities, please contact Captain Calum Grains, CEO (calum@lerwick-harbour.co.uk).

For enquiries regarding any of the Shetland Islands Council (SIC) owned facilities, please contact Claire Christey, Port Engineering Team Leader (claire.christey@shetland.gov.uk).

TIER 1 FACILITY OVERVIEW

This following section presents additional detail at the two Tier 1 facilities: Greenhead Base and Dales Voe. Details of Tier 2 and Tier 3 facilities are included as Appendix 1 to this document. Figure 4 (below) highlights the location of the Tier 1 facilities within Lerwick Harbour.

Figure 4: Lerwick Harbour ports location map (Credit: ESB (left))

Greenhead Base

Figure 5: Greenhead Base berth plan (source: Adapted from LPA)

Greenhead Base is comprised of 7 berths across a 785m suspended deck concrete quay, with water depths ranging from -6m to -9m Chart Datum (CD). It is an all-weather, 24/7/365 facility, with shipping access to the North and South via a wide channel (minimum 120m) through Lerwick Harbour. The facility features large, modern concrete quaysides that were initially built in 1997/98 and further extended in 2012/13. Its versatility allows for the support of anything from standard cargo supply work to large-scale offshore projects.

The naturally sheltered quayside is equipped with heavy lift pads at berths 4 and 6, meaning that Greenhead Base offers comprehensive infrastructure for various operations. The turning basin and manoeuvring area have recently been expanded to approximately 450m x 250m x -9m CD, enhancing manoeuvrability for vessels.

Covering an area of over 160,000m², Greenhead Base has recently expanded its footprint, with an additional 45,000m² to the north and new laydown extensions to the south (see Component Laydown & Storage, Figure 12 -Figure 14). With seven berths in total, it serves as a multi-purpose service base, with all quays being operated by LPA and available for common use. Additionally, there is a licensed decommissioning pad (operated by Peterson, with waste handling license currently held by Veolia) spanning 20,000m², along with on-site engineering and fabrication facilities. Work is also currently underway on a new purpose-built facility for subsea decommissioning waste management behind berth 6, which will be similar to the larger decom pad operated by Peterson / Veolia, but around 1/10th of the size.

Both the northern and southern harbours boast water depths exceeding 50m (bathymetry maps presented in Wet Storage and Marshalling Options, Figure 19Figure 20), further enhancing the base's capabilities and accessibility for various maritime activities.

There is significant ambition to support the offshore wind industry from the facilities at Greenhead Base (covered in the 'Future Port Infrastructure' section of this report), by the local supply chain, Peterson Shetland, and the LPA. The LPA will work to accommodate as many operations across Lerwick Harbour as possible to meet demand. It is likely however that the Lerwick Harbour facilities will be in increasingly high demand as the decade progresses, with competition for quayside project delivery space likely coming from other offshore wind project developments, decommissioning, and the oil & gas sector.

Greenhead Base Data Table

Location	North entrance to Lerwick Harbour (60° 10' N 01° 09' W)
Sea Approach	Quaysides accessed via North Entrance channel, which is 120m wide and dredged to a minimum depth of -9.1m CD, allowing shipping access 24/7 in all weathers. Max significant wave height within turning basin < 0.7 m.
Quayside Water Depth	Overall: -6.0 to -9.1m CD South Quay: 450m of quay length has water depth -9.0m CD (berths 4-7), remainder has depth of -8.0m CD (berth 3) North Quay: -6.0m CD (berths 1 & 2)
Tidal Conditions	MHWS +2.2m CD, MLWS +0.5m CD
Quay Details	Quaysides heights are +3.4 m CD South Quay: Heavy duty tyre fenders present between Trellix rubber 'V' fenders at 5.5m centres 32 x 50/75te capacity 'Mushroom' head type bollards located at 22m centres 1 x 150Te Heavy Duty Bollard North Quay: Panel fenders with UHMW – PE low friction face pads at 5.5m centres along entirety of berths 1 & 2 19 x 30Te 'Tee' head type bollards located at 11mm centres 1 x 150Te Heavy Duty Bollard
Load Capacities	General quay strength (suspended quay deck slab): 5.3Te/m ² UDL Heavier loads can be accommodated by load-spreading or focusing loads on supporting steel piles (e.g. GARP subsea project stored 400Te of large riser transportation reels on the quayside) Heavy lift pads: 33Te/m ² UDL each, designed to accommodate 1000Te lift from a mobile crane.
Quay Length	South Quay (berths 3 to 7): 570 m North Quay (berths 1 & 2): 215m Total: 785m
Component Laydown and Storage	Estimated total of 154,000m ² outside storage area Large warehousing/internal and external storage available on site from Peterson Shetland Limited and indoor storage available at Streamline Shipping Group.

<p>Main uses and users</p>	<p>Greenhead Base is predominantly used as project support and offshore operations base. Historically, the base has serviced the North Sea oil & gas industry, supporting large field development projects, although the facility is now servicing an increasing number of projects in the renewables sector (onshore wind and tidal).</p> <p>The base also serves as an important facility for the aquaculture sector, where on-site clients may lift boats ashore and store equipment and machinery.</p> <p>There are several engineering fabrication firms on-site at Greenhead Base, including Malakoff and Lerwick Engineering Fabrication (LEF).</p>
<p>Additional information</p>	<p>Marine Gas Oil (MGO) and water services are present along all quay sections.</p> <p>No Air Draft restriction.</p> <p>No harbour maintenance dredging requirement.</p> <p>Two assistance pilot boats/tugs available from LPA (21 to 24 Te bollard pull).</p> <p>Harbour Crane available for hire (100Te @ 18m radius to 29Te @ 44m radius).</p> <p>Available services include warehouse storage and distribution services, labour resources, forklifts, mobile cranes, trucks, bunkering services, vessel agency services etc.</p> <p>Deep, unobstructed and sheltered anchorages available in close proximity to Greenhead Base (North/South Lerwick Harbour @ 30 to 50m water depths) and 2km away at Dales Voe.</p>

Table 5: Greenhead Base data table

Dales Voe

Figure 6: Dales Voe facility plan (source: Adapted from LPA)

Dales Voe serves as a prominent oil platform decommissioning facility which can be operated 24/7. Specifically designed to handle Single Lift Topside and Jacket Structures, it can also accommodate the direct load-in of smaller structures, catering to the diverse needs of the offshore industry.

Originally constructed by the LPA in 1980, Dales Voe underwent significant expansions, first in 2017 to increase load capacities to 60Te/m², and then again in 2020 to accommodate the substantial loadings associated with the delivery and single-piece decommissioning of the largest offshore structures. Its strategic proximity to Greenhead Base (just 2 km) offers the potential for multiple or large-scale projects to be delivered across both facilities with efficient logistics.

Dales Voe stands out for its capability to accommodate the largest heavy-lift construction vessels in the world, as well as handle large single-lift to piece-small decommissioning projects. One of the deepest and strongest facilities of its kind in the UK, Dales Voe plays a vital role in supporting the offshore industry's project development and decommissioning needs.

Dales Voe Data Table	
Location	Dales Voe, North end of Lerwick Harbour (60° 11' N 01° 10' W)
Sea Approach	The North Approach Channel has water depths > 30m with a 900m channel width at the mouth of the Voe, and is unobstructed. Sheltered area with plentiful turning and manoeuvring space, capable of accommodating the world's largest construction vessels.
Quayside Water Depth	-9.4 to -12.5m CD
Tidal Conditions	MHWS +2.2m CD, MLWS +0.5m CD
Quay Details	Quay height +4.9m CD. Matrix of heavy duty truck tyre fenders between Trellex rubber "V" fenders with low friction UHMW-PE cappings present along full quay length. 5 x 125Te and 4 x 80Te bollards along quay, 3 x 280 and 3 x 100Te onshore. 570m ² office block. 4,950m ² decom slab. 5,550m ² concrete slabs for waste processing. Heavy-duty 180m skid path from quayside to decom slab. >5,000m ² laydown areas. Quayside is a ground bearing slab retained by a tied combi-wall structure. Apron width 50m.
Load Capacities	Deck loading capacity of 60 Te/m ² over the ~2,500m ² quay slab, with equivalent load capacity then available moving back from the quay slab and into the main site Linkspan loads up to 800 Te/m ²
Quay Length	127m
Component Laydown and Storage	50,000m ² outside storage
Main uses and users	Peterson (a prominent international logistics company and leaseholder of 12,000m ² decom pad at Dales Voe) and Veolia (multi-national services company specialising in waste management and decommissioning) have worked in partnership in recent years to deliver large scale decommissioning projects from the Dales Voe facility. The main industries served by Dales Voe are oil & gas decommissioning and

	large scale North Sea project developments.
Additional information	<p>Water services located at quay.</p> <p>No requirement for maintenance dredging.</p> <p>No Air Draft restriction.</p> <p>High waste acceptance limits (250,000Te per day or 1,000,000Te per year, non-hazardous or hazardous).</p> <p>Secluded, self-contained facility.</p> <p>Deep, unobstructed and sheltered anchorages available in close proximity to Dales Voe and 2km away from Greenhead Base.</p>

Table 6: Dales Voe Data Table

FUTURE PORT INFRASTRUCTURE

There are currently several planned expansion and improvement programmes for port infrastructure in Shetland likely to be undertaken over the coming 5 to 10 years. These expansion programmes will materially increase the capacity of the port for supporting offshore wind developments.

Dales Voe Expansion: Ultra-Deep-Water-Quay (UDWQ)

The expansion of the Dales Voe facility will represent the most material increase in Shetland's port capacity, with the construction of the ultra-deep-water-quay. This multi-phase development is being led by the Lerwick Port Authority, with Scottish Government funding support confirmed as part of the Islands Growth Deal for the first phase of the development. The Lerwick Port Authority are currently raising match-funding and are planning to have this phase of the development completed ahead of the first turbine assembly / integration activities towards the end of the decade.

Phase 1 planned development

Figure 7: Dales Voe UDWQ Phase 1 (source: Adapted from LPA)

The initial phase will see the development of an additional 100m long heavy-duty quay to the North of the existing 127m heavy duty quay. With an initial quayside depth of -21m CD, this facility will be capable of accommodating the world's largest crane and construction vessels alongside the quay for direct unloading of structures. The minimum quay strength of the new facility is anticipated to be 25te/m², with up to 60te/m² available across the 2500m² quay slab and the areas behind this on the existing 127m quay.

In addition to the quay development, significant land reclamation is planned, which will provide an additional c.56,000m² of laydown space directly behind the new quay.

The expansion has been planned in such a way as to ensure uninterrupted operation of the existing Dales Voe facility throughout the construction phase.

In total, following completion of the first phase of the Dales Voe UDWQ development, the site will host total quay length of 228m across 2 parallel quays, and a total laydown and project assembly capacity of c.115,000m².

Given the LPA's extensive landholding in Lerwick, there will be future opportunities to further expand facilities in the Dales Voe area beyond the UDWQ project. It should also be noted that the expansion plans described for Phase 1 are fluid in nature and may change depending on funding or operational factors. Regular contact with the LPA to keep abreast of development planning would therefore be advisable.

STRUCTURE LOAD IN/OUT

For the load-in or load-out of large-scale structures associated with offshore wind developments, Greenhead Base and Dales Voe represent the pre-eminent facilities in Shetland, with a theoretical upper weight limit across the quay in excess of 20,000Te. Further relevant details for each of these facilities is outlined within this section.

Dales Voe	Loadbearing capacity	60Te/m ²
	Linkspan line load capacity	>800Te/m
	Theoretical upper capacity	>24,000Te
Greenhead Base	Quay load capacity	5Te/m ² with significantly larger loading possible when directed over piles.
	2 Heavy lift pads (~500m ² and ~700m ²)	33.3te/m ²
	Load relieving slab	Allows large structures (>10,000Te) to transition across the quay and to the laydown areas behind this.

Beyond Greenhead and Dales Voe, Holmsgarth, Mair's Quay, Scalloway, Sullom Voe and Cullivoe are suitable for the load-in of road-transportable structures, either by barge, geared vessel, or mobile crane (subject to sufficient engineered load spreading dependent on ground bearing requirements). Examples of the type of cargoes that these facilities would be suitable for receiving include shipping containers, project plant and equipment, and smaller secondary components that can be transported by road.

Dales Voe

As previously noted, the Dales Voe facility is one of the strongest quaysides in the UK with a loadbearing capacity of 60Te/m², and a linkspan line load capacity of over 800Te/m, due to the heavy-duty double pile construction at the front of the quay. The facility has a theoretical upper capacity of over 24,000Te across the quay.

Figure 8: Ninian North topside load-in at Dales Voe (credit: LPA / Shetland Flyer)

The largest structure loaded across the Dales Voe quay to date was the 14,000Te Ninian North topside (Figure 8). The structure was transferred by barge across the quay using a skid and rail system. Subsequent large structures (8,000Te jacket) have utilised dual concrete gravity strand-jack anchors which have been permanently installed at the rear of the site, and structures have been jacked ashore with steel skid shoes over a Teflon surface.

The contracting structure for the delivery of these scopes was complex, with high levels of local supply chain participation. The scope was executed under CDM regulations, under which the Shetland supply chain are familiar in working.

Greenhead Base Load-In Examples

Greenhead Base features differing load-bearing capacities across the length of the 785m quay. The red areas shown in Figure 9 (below) are of suspended concrete deck construction, which have a load-bearing capacity of $5\text{Te}/\text{m}^2$, with capacity for this to be increased through engineered load spreading. There are 2 heavy lift pads (located at berth 6 and berth 4), which allow large shoreside crange to be set-up, with a load bearing capacity of $33\text{Te}/\text{m}^2$ before engineered load spreading.

The load relieving slab (located adjacent to berth 3), can enable structures weighing in-excess of 10,000Te to be loaded across the quay. Heavy duty piled reinforcements in the laydown area behind berth 3 allow such structured to be set down in close proximity to the quay.

Figure 9: Greenhead Base indicative load capacities (source: Peterson Shetland)

Whilst $10\text{Te}/\text{m}^2$ is used as a rule of thumb for much of the site behind the suspended deck, there is significant scope for engineered load spreading or further civil reinforcement works (such as those undertaken at berth 3).

Figure 10: Frigg module load-in at berth 3 (credit: Peterson Shetland)

Figure 10 (above) shows 10,000Te being taken across the quay by barge and 366 SPMT axels at Greenhead Base berth 3, after reinforcement and load-relieving civil works were undertaken to enable the structure to be transported across the quay.

Figure 11 Viking windfarm components taken ashore at Greenhead Base (credit: Peterson Shetland)

Greenhead Base has also been proven suitable for the handling of wind turbine components (Figure 11), with over 1,000 components received, stored, and transported from the site during 2023 for the 443MW Viking Energy onshore wind farm.

In addition to the development planning for Dales Voe, work has also been undertaken by the Shetland supply chain (Norm Alliance) to consider spatial and facility requirements at Greenhead Base to support floating sub-structure component load-in, assembly and load-out, with up to 4 simultaneous assembly bays possible.

COMPONENT LAYDOWN & STORAGE

This section sets out prospective laydown and storage for the Tier 1 facilities in Shetland. For maps of open storage at Tier 2 & 3 sites, please refer to Appendix 1.

Note: Laydown areas shown here may be subject to existing lease agreements, and their inclusion should not be interpreted as their availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

	Facility name	Current Laydown / Open Storage (m ²)
Locations suitable for storing and handling very large structures and equipment (e.g. substructures, chains & moorings, turbine components, etc.)	Greenhead Base	160,000
	Dales Voe	50,000
Locations suitable for storing and handling mid-sized structures and equipment (e.g. secondary steel, plant and equipment, 40ft shipping containers, etc.)	Holmsgarth & Mair's	21,800
	Sullom Voe Construction Jetty	13,000
	Scalloway	8,400
	Cullivoe	17,000
Locations suitable for storing or handling very small equipment (e.g. palletised goods, small containers, etc)	Sella Ness	0 (warehousing nearby)
	Collafirth	1,400
	Walls	250
	West Burrafirth	900
	Broonies Taing (road transport only)	0 (warehousing nearby)
	Baltasound	1,500
	Uyeasound	1,000
	Fetlar (Hamars Ness)	3,500
	Whalsay (Symbister)	1,500
	Out Skerries	600
Locations not currently equipped to store or handle goods of any size	Toft	0
	Burra (Hamnavoe)	0
	Mid Yell	400
	Fair Isle	0

Table 7: Laydown and open storage assessment

Greenhead Base laydown & storage

Greenhead base is the largest open storage facility in Shetland, with over 150,000m² of mixed-surface laydown. South Greenhead is a mixture of heavy-duty concrete surfaces, and compacted aggregate over bedrock. These storage sites are in high demand due to their proximity to the main quayside.

North Greenhead doesn't feature a quayside, and so any equipment stored here must be transported from the quay at South Greenhead. The site is reclaimed land, and the surface is compacted aggregate, capable of supporting heavy loads (sample plate load tests included in appendices).

Figure 12: Greenhead Base all laydown areas

Figure 13: Greenhead Base south laydown detail

Figure 14: Greenhead Base North laydown detail

Dales Voe laydown & storage

Dales Voe's heavy duty laydown area is suitable for handling and storing extremely large structures. The site lends itself to dedicated project operations due to its single point of access and dedicated quay. The short distance to Greenhead Base means that the two facilities can be complimentary in storing and handling equipment for the same large-scale projects.

Figure 15: Dales Voe laydown detail

ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

Fuel

Marine Gas Oil (MGO) can be supplied across all Lerwick Harbour berths by road tanker. Quayside fuel points at Greenhead Base, Holmsgarth and Mair's Quay can supply large volumes of MGO by pipeline. Scalloway Harbour has MGO tanks and vessel refuelling infrastructure, although this is understood to now be redundant, meaning that vessels using that facility will require refueling by road tanker from the main fuel depots in Lerwick.

Several smaller ports (Tiers 2 & 3) can provide limited fuel supplies, generally for smaller vessels (e.g. yachts), available at Cullivoe, West Burrafirth, Baltasound, Uyeasound, Hamars Ness and Symbister. Otherwise, MGO can be supplied via road tanker (excluding Fair Isle).

Water

Water is available at most Lerwick Harbour berths via 2.5 inch diameter water hose connections, 40 to 50 Te/hour delivery rate.

Tier 2 and 3 ports can provide limited water supplies for smaller vessels (e.g. yachts), except Hamars Ness on Fetlar, which relies on water supply delivered from Cullivoe.

Power

Shore power connections are available across Holmsgarth and Mair's, available as:

- 16 amp, 32 amp and 63 amp connections in the 240 volt, single phase range
- 125 amp, 200 amp and 250 amp connections in the 415 volt, three phase range

Dales Voe and Greenhead Base does not provide shore power connections.

Apart from Scalloway Harbour, Cullivoe and Toft, most of the Tier 2 and 3 ports do not provide shore power connections.

WET STORAGE & MARSHALLING

This section sets out considerations associated with wet storage and marshalling activities which could be required for the delivery of an offshore wind development project from Shetland.

Wet storage and marshalling options

There are many sheltered areas around the coastline of Shetland which could host anchorages for a small number of assembled floating structures (1 to 3 units), but as the number of potential floating structures increase, so too the number of suitable anchorages decreases.

One key consideration is the level of exposure to tidal action. The fast-moving tides through Yell and Bluemull Sounds (Bluemull Sound has a tidal range of 2.1m and tidal speeds of 0.2-1.0m/s, with more than all the water in all the rivers in the mainland UK combined flowing through each sound, each day) mean the otherwise sheltered locations are likely unsuitable for wet storage of marshalling of completed floating structures.

Figure 16: Shetland facility map

Figure 17: Shetland tidal map (source: SIC / Natural Power)

Potential wet storage and marshalling sites have been screened against the following criteria: exposure of the site to poor environmental conditions (weather and tidal), proximity to services (such as project support base, and bases for workboats, tugs, crew transfer vessels, etc.), proximity to the eventual Stoura Wind Farm development site for final tow-out, impact on environment (human impact and natural impact), interference with existing industries (such as aquaculture or inshore fisheries).

Figure 18: Shortlisted anchorage sites

After initial screening, five prospective wet storage and marshalling locations were shortlisted. They were ranked as follows (1 being most suitable, 5 being least suitable of the short-listed locations):

Site Name	Exposure	Service Proximity	Stoura OWF Proximity	Impacts	Ranking / (Overall score)
North Lerwick	2	1	2	1	1 (6)
South Lerwick	1	2	3	2	2 (8)
Scalloway	3	3	4	3	3 (13)
South-East Yell	4	4	1	5 (=)	4 (14)
St Magnus Bay	5	5	5	5 (=)	5 (20)

Table 8: Wet storage and marshalling screening

North Lerwick

The North Lerwick wet storage and marshalling locations scored highest in the screening exercise, due in part to their proximity to the Tier 1 facilities and associated established port services, and were believed to have the lowest impact on people and existing industries (such as inshore fisheries and aquaculture).

Figure 19: North Lerwick wet storage / anchorages (source: LPA / UK Hydrographic Office)

South Lerwick

The South Lerwick wet storage and marshalling locations scored second highest in the screening exercise, again due in part to their proximity to the Tier 1 facilities and associated established port services. This is the most sheltered of the 5 shortlisted sites, with the lowest environmental impact, but higher human impact than North Lerwick due to its prominent location.

Figure 20: South Lerwick wet storage / anchorages (source: LPA / UK Hydrographic Office)

Other shortlisted sites

Scalloway harbour is relatively sheltered and does have access to material quayside infrastructure and the potential for associated port services. However, human impacts are considered to be high due to visual impact, and potential for disruption to inshore fisheries and aquaculture activities. Scalloway's location on the West coast of Shetland would mean a longer and more complex tow-out operation than other sites on the East coast of Shetland.

South-East Yell is the closest marshalling, wet storage / anchorage location to the Stoura development site and supply base services could potentially be established out of Cullivoe or Lerwick. However, the relative exposure of the site would be moderately high, and environmental and human impacts (e.g. impact on inshore fisheries) would be high.

The largest shortlisted site at St. Magnus Bay was clearly the least suitable of screened sites, scoring last in every category due to its distance from services, being furthest from the Stoura development site, the exposure to North Atlantic storms, and the human and environmental impacts.

Although South-East Yell scored behind Scalloway in the screening exercise, its proximity to the Stoura development site and potential for support services to be built-out in nearby facilities (such as Cullivoe) could merit further exploration, if additional options are required beyond Lerwick Harbour.

SHETLAND SUPPLY CHAIN

Shetland hosts an experienced engineering supply chain that is significantly larger in comparative terms than other communities of Shetland's size in the UK. This is predominantly due to the development of some of Europe's largest oil & gas infrastructure in and around Shetland over the past 50 years, and the thriving aquaculture sector, which is 3 times larger in economic terms than the oil and gas sector.

Over 1,000 people are employed in Shetland's energy and engineering sectors, much of these people directly employed within locally-owned supply chain businesses. In total, the local engineering and energy services supply chain (including logistics, port services and transportation) has the capacity to turn-over circa £100 million per year.

Shetland supply chain businesses

If you would like your business to be listed in this report, please email info@voarenergy.com and we will revise this section of the report.

Aquila Waste Management Ltd

Description:

Aquila own and operate waste management services in Shetland. The business was acquired in 2023 from TWMA. They operate the Vatsetter Waste Management Facility in the Central Mainland

Services:

Aquila's facility is licensed under Pollution Prevention Control (PPC) regulations as a hazardous waste transfer station. They are equipped with all the necessary technology and equipment to collect, store, and transfer hazardous wastes safely and compliantly. Full traceability and certification for waste tracking and compliance.

Contact: Aquila Waste Management Services, Tingwall, Shetland. Tel: 01595 840431

Arch Henderson LLP

Description:

Arch Henderson are a team of over 70 engineering and architecture consultants, operating throughout the UK and abroad to provide multi-discipline services throughout a project's lifetime.

Services:

- Maritime, structural, civil and mechanical engineering consultancy
- Project management
- Geotechnical investigations
- Renewables consultancy

Arch Henderson were closely involved in the extension and redevelopment of the Dales Voe South Quay in 2017, resulting in the creation of the UK's heaviest duty quay.

Contact: Address: Stewart Building, Esplanade, Lerwick, ZE1 0LL Tel: 01595 695512 Fax: 01595 694401
Web: www.arch-henderson.co.uk

B.K. Marine Limited

Description:

B.K. Marine provide multi-purpose work boat hire and marine logistics with a four boat fleet, teamed with crew and staff, available for hire.

Services:

- Lifting
- Fendering
- Salmon farm work
- Towing
- Fishing /survey
- Salvage/diving

Delivering Yokohama Fenders
in Sullom Voe Terminal

Contact: Address: Herrislea House, Shetland, ZE2 9SB Tel: 01592 840208 Email: boats@herrisleahouse.co.uk Web: www.bkmarine.co.uk

Civil and Structural Engineering Shetland (CASE) Limited

Description:

CASE Shetland is a local company which provides high quality design and consultancy services across a range of disciplines.

Services:

- Civil engineering
- Structural engineering
- Architectural design
- Project management
- Topographical surveys
- Site supervision

Contact: Address: 4 Market Street, Lerwick, ZE1 0JN Tel: 01595 840 476 Email: info@caseshetland.co.uk

Clarkson Port Services

Description:

Clarksons employ > 1,800 people across the world and are global leaders in maritime consultancy and shipping services.

Services:

Ship agency services, including:

- Crew change management
- Port logistics
- Ships spares
- Procurement services

Contact: Address: Block 2, Greenhead Base, Gremista, Lerwick, ZE1 0PY Tel: 01595 695717 Email: lerwick@clarksons.com Web: www.clarksons.com

CW Johnson Plant Ltd

Description:

Shetland-based plant hire and civil contracting company

Services:

- Plant hire
- Civil engineering construction and contract works
- Haulage

Contact: Address: CWJ Plant, Greenhead Base, Gremista Industrial Estate, Shetland ZE1 0PY Tel: 01595 502160

Delta Marine Limited

Description:

Delta Marine has provided modern, high specification, maneuverable anchor handling tugs and work boats for several decades. With two DP multicats in the fleet, Delta Marine specializes in offshore wind and tidal energy installations.

Services:

- Vessels chartering
- Operation and maintenance
- Workboat and Marine Services

DP II Renewable Service Vessel Voe Vanguard

Hydraulic cranes of Voe Viking multipurpose tug

Contact: Address: 2/2 Mounthooly Street, Lerwick, ZE1 0BJ Tel: 01595 694799 Fax: 01595 692685 Web: www.delta-marine.co.uk

Denholm Port Services Limited

Description:

Denholm Port Services provide ship agency across all major UK ports, including Lerwick Harbour.

Services:

- Ship agency
- Stevedoring
- Warehousing & distribution
- Lay-up services
- Customs clearance
- Chartering

Contact: Address: Greenhead Base, Lerwick, ZE1 0PY Tel: 01595 720402 Email: enquiries@denholm-portservices.com Web: www.denholm-portservices.com

D.H. Marine Limited

Description:

Shetland-based engineering services, plant hire and supplies.

Services:

- Electrical and mechanical engineering
- Hose making & pressure testing
- Testing and compliance services
- Plant hire
- Marine supplies

Contact: Address: D. H. Marine Ltd. Marina Business Park, Gremista, Lerwick, ZE1 0TA Tel: 01595 690618 Fax: 01595 690619 Web: www.dhmarine.co.uk

EMN Plant Limited

Description:

Shetland-based plant hire, haulage, quarrying and civil contractors

Services:

- Plant hire
- Haulage
- Quarrying
- Civil engineering contract works
- Garage services
- Scrap metal recycling

Contact: Address: EMN Plant Ltd, Sella Ness, Graven, Shetland, ZE2 9UP Tel: 01806 242 882 Fax: 01806 242 887 Web: www.emnplant.co.uk

GAC Shipping (UK) Limited

Description:

GAC Group is one of the world's largest shipping agencies, handling over 6,000 ships in the UK per year, and has a branch office in Lerwick.

Services:

- Ship agency
- Launch services
- Bunker fuels
- Husbandry services
- Project logistics

Contact: Address: Greenhead Base, Lerwick, ZE1 0PY Tel: 01595 880463 Web: www.gac.com

Garriock Bros. Ltd.

Description:

Garriock Bros. Ltd. is Shetland-based, operating across the UK. The company provides a diverse range of civil engineering, house building, plant hire, quarry operations, contract crushing, machine sales and window manufacturing services.

Services:

- Construction & Civil Engineering
- Quarry Operations
- Plant / Tool Hire & Sales
- New & Used Plant & Equipment Sales
- Haulage
- Skip Hire
- Marine Sales

Contact: Address: Unit 30, Gremista Industrial Estate, Lerwick, Shetland, ZE1 0PX Tel: 01595 694765
Web: <https://www.garriock.co.uk>

HNP Engineers Limited

Description:

HNP engineers have been providing local engineering services and supplies for 50 years.

Services:

- Marine, general and hydraulic engineering
- Repair and maintenance of ships and boats
- Engineering supplies, including oil delivery

Contact: Address: 5 & 6 Lower Blackhill Industrial Estate, Lerwick, ZE1 0AE Tel: 01595 692493 Email: hnpoffice@btconnect.com

Highland Fuels Limited

Description:

Highland Fuels provide a range of fuels and lubricants in Scotland and beyond.

Services:

- Supply commercial, marine and vehicular fuels, oils and lubricants

Contact: Address: 3 Esplanade, Lerwick, ZE1 0LL Tel: 01595 694348 Fax: 01595 695682 Web: www.highlandfuels.co.uk

H. Williamson & Sons Limited

Description:

Marine electronic company based in Scalloway, Shetland. H. Williamson & Sons Ltd. have decades of experience in the supply, installation and maintenance of marine electronic equipment.

Services:

- Marine electronics services
- Underwater camera and communications repair
- Telecommunication and microwave infrastructure support
- Onshore radar & VTS support services

CCTV upgrade for LHD in 2011

Equipment supply and installation for Halcyon LK467 vessel in 2012.

Contact: Address: Main Street, Scalloway, ZE1 0TR Tel: 01595 880645 Fax: 01595 880535 Web: www.hwilliamson.co.uk

Lerwick Engineering and Fabrication Limited

Description:

LEF have 30 years of experience providing various engineering solutions in Shetland, within the oil & gas, decommissioning, marine, renewable and utility industries.

Services:

- Engineering
- Marine & vessel mobilisations (e.g. sea-fastening)
- Rigging & lifting
- Barge works
- Project management
- Welding & fabrication
- Electrical & plumbing work
- Coatings
- Maintenance & repairs

Fabrication of a large scale atmospheric vent for Sullom Voe power station

Servicing of large vessels, including ROV fittings, grillages, grit blasting etc.

Contact: Address: Greenhead Base, Gremista, Lerwick, ZE1 0PY Tel: 01595 692349 Fax: 01595 692963
Web: www.lefltd.co.uk

L.H.D. Marine Supplies Limited

Description:

Long-established Shetland-based marine supplies and services.

Services:

- Testing & Certification of Rigging & Lifting Equipment
- Marine supplies
- Net construction/ mending
- Fuel supplies
- Wire store

L.H.D. road tanker delivering fuel

Well-stocked Wire Store

Contact: Address: 1 Alexandra Buildings, Lerwick, ZE1 0LL Tel: 01595 692882 Fax: 01595 695619 Web: www.lhdmarinesupplies.co.uk

L & M Engineering (UK) Limited

Description:

Shetland-based marine & industrial engineering services.

Services:

- Mechanical & electrical engineering
- Welding & fabrication
- Component supply
- Motor control & automation design
- Diesel engine servicing

Re-fit and re-power of Sharyn Louise vessel in 2017, including main switchboard installation (right)

Contact: Address: Garthspool Road, Lerwick, ZE1 0NY Tel: 01595 692522 Fax: 01595 693601 Web: www.landengineering.co.uk

Lerwick Port Authority

Description:

The Lerwick Port Authority (LPA) manages port activities across Lerwick Harbour, including Holmsgarth & Mairs pier, Dales Voe and Greenhead Base facilities. Two LPA Harbour tugs are available for pilotage on request, with 21.4 and 24 tonne bollard pull.

Services:

- Berthing facilities for various vessel types
- Pilotage services for safe navigation within port limits
- Towage assistance for manoeuvring vessels in and out of port
- Mooring services to secure vessels at berths
- Provision of laydown and storage
- Emergency response and assistance

Contact: Address: Albert Building, Lerwick, ZE1 0LL Tel: 01595 692991 Fax: 01595 693452 Web: www.lerwick-harbour.co.uk

Malakoff Limited

Description:

Long-established, Shetland-based engineering and fabrication contractor, providing expert services in marine engineering, oil and gas, utilities and renewable sectors.

Services:

- Project management
- Aquaculture support
- Coatings
- Diving
- Inspection, testing & certification
- Marine construction & civil engineering
- Marine supplies
- Renewables (e.g. wind turbine installation)
- Ship repair
- Welding & fabrication
- Mechanical engineering support
- Fabrication

Contact: Address: North Ness, Lerwick, ZE1 0LZ Tel: 01595 695544 Fax: 01595 695720 Web: www.malakofflimited.co.uk

Ness Engineering Ltd

Description:

Ness Engineering is an established Electrical, Mechanical and Building Services company.

Services:

- Provision of modular worksite offices
- Specialisation in electrical, instrumentation, and control systems, and the hire of equipment
- Design of bespoke engineering solutions
- Maintenance and support services for ongoing operations and facilities

Contact: Ness Engineering, The Brakes, Virkie, Shetland, ZE3 9JW. Tel: 01950 460714. Email: office@nessengineering.com

Nortech Marine Limited

Description:

Shetland-based welding and fabrication company.

Services:

- Welding & fabrication
- Industrial painting and blasting
- Abrasive waterjet cutting

General fabrication, blasting and paint work is ongoing at Lerwick power station

Recent maintenance work on Antares fishing vessel

Contact: Address: Harbourview Workshop, Gremista, Lerwick, ZE1 0PX Tel: 01595 696118 Mob: 07990 785097 Web: www.nortechmarine.co.uk

Northwards Limited

Description:

Specialist freight transport and delivery service for Shetland, Orkney and North of Scotland. Over 40 people are employed locally to manage an 18 vehicle fleet in Shetland.

Services:

- Bulk cargo, full or part load road and sea transport
- Skip hire
- Warehousing
- Temperature – controlled transport
- Dangerous good transport

Contact: Address: Anderson Base, Gremista, Lerwick, ZE1 0PX Tel: 01595 694452 Fax: 01595 694920 Web: www.northwardsltd.co.uk

Ocean Kinetics Limited

Description:

Shetland-based marine engineering services. Ocean Kinetics employ over 100 people and provide engineering fabrication and marine services (via divers and workboats) for the oil & gas, renewables, fishing, aquaculture and decommissioning sectors.

Services:

- Welding
- Fabrication
- Machining
- Mechanical services
- Inspection
- Diving
- Survey work

Ocean Kinetics were the main contractor for the handling of 3,500te structures at Greenhead Base with a floating shear-leg crane

Contact: Address: Port Business Park, Gremista, Lerwick, ZE1 0TW Tel: 01595 696707 Fax: 01595 697040 Web: www.oceankinetics.co.uk

Peterson Shetland Limited

Description: Peterson Shetland is a prominent logistics and service provider, who operate the Greenhead Base facility and hold a lease on the decommissioning pad at Dales Voe

Services:

- Managed lifting services
- Cranage and crane hire
- Energy Logistics
- Stevedore services
- Warehousing
- Open Storage
- Marine fuel banking

Contact: Address: Greenhead Base, Gremista, Lerwick, ZE1 0PY Tel: 01595 694242 Fax: 01595 692767 Web: www.onepeterson.com

Pure Energy Centre Limited

Description:

Pure Energy Centre (PEC) is a manufacturer of small, medium and large scale renewable energy systems, including wind turbines, hydrogen systems, solar PV, nitrogen systems and oxygen systems.

Services:

- Renewable energy consultancy
- Design, development, manufacture and installation of renewable energy products (e.g. electrolyzers, small wind turbines)

Contact: Address: Unit 3, Hagdale Industrial Estate, Baltasound, Unst, Shetland ZE2 9DS Tel: 01957 711 410 Email: info@pureenergycentre.com

R. S. Henderson Limited

Description:

R. S. Henderson provides Shetland-based haulage links to the UK Mainland and supplies, primarily for the fishing industry. The company has a fleet of 11 trucks and 25 trailers, hosted in their Cullivoe and Scalloway bases.

Services:

- Haulage
- Supply feed, gas, coal, aggregates and concrete mix
- 24-hour ice and fuel service
- Commercial servicing e.g. brake testing, tyre changing

Contact: Address: Cullivoe, Yell, Shetland, ZE2 9DD Tel: 01957 744248 Fax: 01957 744248 Web: www.rshenderson.com

Seletar Shipping Limited

Description:

Seletar have 8 locations across the UK, including Lerwick, and are the current leading ship agent for UK Oil and Gas.

Services:

Ship agency services, including:

- Freight management
- Crew co-ordination
- On-shore logistics
- Procurement services

Contact: Address: Holmsgarth Quay, Lerwick, ZE1 0PW Tel: 01595 694504 Email: lerwick@seletar.com
Web: www.seletar.ascoworld.com

Shetland Transport Limited

Description:

Shetland-established freight and haulage business, which is now owned and operated by DFDS and connects Shetland to the UK mainland and European continent. The fleet comprises 35 trucks and over 96 trailers.

Services:

- National/ international, full/ part load road transport
- Temperature-controlled transport
- Special cargo
- Parcel and home deliveries

Contact: Address: Greenhead, Lerwick, ZE1 0PY Tel: 01595 695792 Fax: 01595 693722 Web: www.shetlandtransport.com

Streamline Shipping Group

Description:

Global freight, logistics and haulage specialists. Streamline employ over 80 staff across Orkney and Shetland, and have recently expanded operations (Jan 2024) across the isles to become the primary logistics presence.

Services:

- Lifting
- Distribution
- Storage
- Import/export
- Stevedoring
- Chartering

Contact: Address: Garthspool Road, Lerwick, ZE1 0NP Tel: 01595 692869 Fax: 01595 692234 Web: www.streamlineshippinggroup.com

Tulloch Developments Limited

Description:

Civil and marine engineering contractor with over 40 years of experience in Shetland.

Services:

- Marine & civil engineering
- Crane hire
- Plant hire
- Survey work
- Concrete supply
- Quarry operation
- Heavy haulage
- Lay down & storage

Tulloch Developments completed construction of the new pier, slipway and industrial site at Uyeasound, Unst, 2009.

Installation of fibre optic cable from Sandwick to Lerwick

Contact: Address: Gremista, Lerwick, ZE1 0PX Tel: 01595 741427 Fax: 01595 741249 Web: www.tullochdev.co.uk

Veolia UK Limited

Description:

Veolia are the UK leader in resource management, providing a comprehensive range of waste, water and energy management systems, and are global leaders in decarbonizing, saving and regenerating resources.

Services:

- Decommissioning, demolition and land remediation
- Industrial site services and facilities management
- Decarbonising energy
- Water solutions
- Waste management

Contact: Web: www.veolia.co.uk

Voar Energy Limited

Description: Voar is an energy transition consultancy providing technical and policy expertise across three sectors: offshore renewables, hydrogen/power-to-X and maritime decarbonisation.

Services:

- Technical consultancy
- Socio-economic modelling
- Feasibility studies
- Owner's engineering services

Contact: Address: 4 Bank Lane, Lerwick, ZE1 0DS Email: info@voarenergy.com

Accommodation

Securing suitable accommodation can be a challenge in Shetland, particularly where large infrastructure or energy development projects result in a sharp increase in the population. In the past, this has also put significant pressure on the local housing market. Novel solutions are therefore required to minimise the impact of future energy projects in the Isles, and developers should consider whether projects are of a scale that the construction of new housing and accommodation is required. The Shetland Gas Plant took this approach, with the construction of the Moorfield Hotel (demolished after a fire), and the Sella Ness Accommodation facility, and addressed peak worker numbers through the chartering of accommodation barges, which were based in Lerwick and Scalloway.

Several hotels, small guesthouses and self-catering facilities are distributed sparsely across Shetland, but mainly focused in Lerwick.

Contact details for the larger hotels in Shetland are summarised in the table below. This table includes Sella Ness camp, which is a 426-bedroom facility, built in 2011 to accommodate workers for the nearby Shetland Gas Plant. At present, the future of Sella Ness camp is unclear; the camp has temporary planning permission until the end of 2025, but without further extension to planning permissions, the building may be dismantled.

Tier 1 facilities are located within 1-5 miles of the Lerwick guesthouses and hotels by road (The Shetland Hotel, The Lerwick Hotel, The Grand Hotel and The Queen's Hotel). The proximity of Tier 2 and 3 port facilities to nearby hotel accommodation is detailed in the appendix.

Hotel Directory (B&Bs not included)

The Shetland Hotel (64 rooms)

Address: Holmsgarth Road, Lerwick, ZE1 0PW
Tel: 01595 695515

The Lerwick Hotel (34 rooms)

Address: 15 South Road, Lerwick, ZE1 0RB
Tel: 01595 692166

The Grand Hotel (22 rooms)

Address: 149 Commercial Street, Lerwick, ZE1 0AB

Tel: 07828 129158

Queen's Hotel (27 Rooms)

Address: 24 Commercial Street, Lerwick, ZE1 0AB

Tel: 01595 692826

The Maryfield Hotel (4 Rooms)

Address: Maryfield, Bressay, Shetland, ZE2 9EL

Tel: 01595 820203

The Scalloway Hotel (23 rooms)

Address: Main Street, Scalloway, ZE1 0TR

Tel: 01595 880444

St Magnus Bay Hotel (26 rooms)

Address: Hillswick, ZE2 9RW

Tel: 01806 503372

Brae Hotel (35 rooms)

Address: Brae, ZE2 9QJ

Tel: 01806 522 456

Busta House Hotel (22 rooms)

Address: Busta, Brae, ZE2 9QN

Tel: 018096 522506

Baltasound Hotel (24 rooms)

Address: Baltasound, Unst, ZE2 9DS

Tel: 01957 711334

Sella Ness Accommodation (426 rooms)

Address: Sella Ness Industrial Estate, Sullom Voe, ZE2 9QR

Tel: 01806 242114

APPENDIX: TIER 2 & 3 FACILITY DETAILS

Holmsgarth & Mair's Quay

Position: South entrance to Lerwick Harbour (60° 09' N 01° 09' W)

Port infrastructure:

Quays & Piers

Holmsgarth Quay height: +3.6m to +4.7m CD

Mair's Quay height: +4.0m CD

Concrete unloading ramp at Holmsgarth 4

Heavy truck tyre fenders located along full quay length

Pneumatic floating "Yokohama" type fenders available at request

50 x 80te bollards located along quays at 15-20m intervals

Main uses and users:

Holmsgarth & Mair's support a very wide variety of users. The largest of these user groups, active all year round, is the fisheries sector, from smaller whitefish vessels to large pelagic trawlers.

Oil & gas project and services vessels are regular visitors to Holmsgarth year-round. The summer months typically see the facilities busy with mid-sized cruise liners.

Shetland's main lifeline ferry services (passenger and freight vessels) to the Scottish mainland dock each day at Holmsgarth (berths 2 & 3), all year round.

Outside Storage:

Holmsgarth & Mair's are less suitable for open storage of very large structures or equipment, due in part to the large variety of sectors they serve, and the demand for the limited available areas from these sectors. Where these facilities can play an important role is in the short-term staging of project plant and equipment (e.g. modular accommodation units), prior to it being mobilised to the project site.

There is a recent example of large a craneage fleet being offloaded by chartered RORO vessel, and the equipment being temporarily staged at Holmsgarth & Mair's during mobilisation and demobilisation from Shetland.

Port layout:

Facilities and services:

Water services and MGO points present at quay.
 Various shore power options available for vessels.
 Sewage connection into Lerwick waste system at Holmsgarth 4 & 5.

Nearby accommodation:

The Shetland Hotel is adjacent to Holmsgarth
 Several other hotels (The Lerwick Hotel, The Grand Hotel, The Queen's Hotel) and guesthouses are available within Lerwick (1-2 miles from Holmsgarth by road)

Infrastructure constraints:

-

Additional information:

General loading of 10Te/m²
 Subject to consultation, heavy lift pads available for significantly higher loadings.

Laydown areas shown may be subject to existing lease agreements, and their inclusion should not be interpreted as their availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Scalloway Harbour

Position: 60° 08' N 01° 16' W

Main uses and users:

Port infrastructure:

Quays & Piers

Large slip way for repairs can accommodate vessels up to 33m LOA, 4.25m draft, 88m beam and 350Te Dwt.

Busy commercial port used by fishing and aquaculture industry

Outside Storage:

Facilities and services:

Commercial Quay hosts a bunker facility with 500m³ capacity and max delivery rate of 85 m³/hr, available 24/7 by arrangement with ship's local agent.

Bunkers also available by road tanker at all berths.

Bunkers can be transferred from bunker barge while alongside.

Cranes (up to 220Te), forklifts, provisions and water available at each pier on request.

Work boat & tugs up to 90Te bollard pull available.

Nearby accommodation:

- < 1 mile to Scalloway hotel by road
- 6 to 7 miles to Lerwick

Additional information:

Approach channel has minimum depth of -8.7m CD between buoys in vicinity of Port Arthur.

Under keel clearance of 0.5 required at all times within harbour area

Pilotage is compulsory for vessels carrying passengers or notifiable dangerous substances

Laydown areas shown may be subject to existing lease agreements, and their inclusion should not be interpreted as their availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Infrastructure constraints:

Scalloway Harbour is a busy port used predominantly by the fishing and aquaculture industry, which is likely to create competition for berthage, outside storage and parking space.

Sullom Voe Construction Jetty

Position: 60° 27' N 01° 16' W

Main uses and users:

Port infrastructure:

Oil & Gas equipment delivery to SVT / SGP / North Mainland

Pier, slip and laydown

Outside Storage:

Facilities and services:

Jetty Depths are -9.5m CD to -4.5m CD on the South face

-8.7m CD to -5.0m CD on the North face

Deck level is +5.27m CD

Fixed Ro/Ro ramp dimensions 12m x 23.7m, gradient 1.22

Heavy lift pad for Outrigger loads up to 20Te/m2

Nearby accommodation:

- 2 miles to Sella Ness Camp by road
- 7 miles to Brae Hotel by road
- 8 miles to Busta House Hotel by road

Infrastructure constraints:

-

Additional information:

Bunkering by road tanker is not permitted at Sullom Voe Terminal Construction Jetty due to proximity to COMAH site.

Cullivoe

Position: 60° 41' N 01° 00' W

Port infrastructure: Piers, Quays, Marinas

Main uses and users:

Fishing and Aquaculture

Outside Storage:

Facilities and services:

Electric power, limited fuel, ice, stores, net mending, refrigerated road transport & engineering services available.

Nearby accommodation:

There are no hotels on the island of Yell.

- 12 miles to Baltasound Hotel by road and ferry
- 27 miles to Sella Ness Camp by road and ferry
- 32 miles to Brae Hotel by road and ferry
- 33 miles to Busta House Hotel by road and ferry

Infrastructure constraints:

The thin single-track road entrance to Cullivoe pier may limit capacity for heavy road traffic.

Cullivoe pier is busy with the fishing and aquaculture industry, which may create competition for outside storage space and berthage.

Access to major town services on the mainland relies on use of the Yell-Mainland ferry, which has a weight limit of 44 tonnes for a full-articulated unit.

Additional information:

Bluemull Sound has strong tidal stream velocities (0.2-1.0m/s rather than typical <0.25m/s tidal velocities), turbulent races, inshore rocks and can be hazardous with a northerly wind.

Coast requires berth of at least 2 cables.

The sound has a mean annual wave height of 0.2 - 0.6m.

Port approaches dredged to minimum of 5.5m.

Max vessel size 65m.

Laydown areas shown may be subject to existing lease agreements, and their inclusion should not be interpreted as their availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Sella Ness: North Mainland

Position: 60° 26' N 01° 16' W

Main uses and users:

Port infrastructure:

Piers

Sullom Voe tugs and pilot launches are stationed here.
Fishing and leisure vessels.

Outside Storage:

Facilities and services:

Boat Hoist service offered by SIC Ports & Harbours Operations (max vessel width 6m, max vessel weight 50te).

Nearby accommodation:

< 1 mile to Sella Ness Camp by road
5 miles to Brae Hotel by road
6 miles to Busta House Hotel by road

Infrastructure constraints:

Sella Ness pier is used by the Sullom Voe tugs and pilot launches, which may incur competition for berthage

Additional information:

-

Collafirth: North Mainland

Position: 60° 32' N 01° 20' W

Main uses and users:

Port infrastructure:

Fishing and leisure vessels

Pier and Marina

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Water and stores.

Net mending facilities.

Truck access to Scalloway and Lerwick.

Major town services 38 miles by road.

Nearby accommodation:

7.5 miles to St Magnus Bay Hotel by road

13 miles to Brae Hotel and Busta House Hotel by road

Infrastructure constraints:

Toft pier is regularly used for the Mainland-Yell ferry service, which may create conflict of use

Additional information:

Laydown areas shown may be subject to existing lease agreements, and their inclusion should not be interpreted as their availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Toft: North Mainland

Position: 60° 28' 01" N 001° 12' 23" W

Port infrastructure:
 RORO ferry terminal, Marina, New Pier

Main uses and users:
 Mainland-Yell ferry
 Small fishing, aquaculture and leisure vessels

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:
 Water, stores and truck transport to Scalloway and Lerwick are available.
 Ice can be delivered.
 Major town services 27 miles by road.

Nearby accommodation:
 5 miles to Sella Ness Camp by road
 10 miles to Brae Hotel by road
 11 miles to Busta House Hotel by road

Infrastructure constraints:
 Single-track road access to Collafirth pier may limit capacity for heavy road traffic

Additional information:
 New pier was constructed in 2021 using sheet piles and internal tie rods, filled with crushed rock, and a reinforced concrete deck slab.
 Deck infrastructure includes 30t bollards, 1000mm diameter tyre fenders on most berths and Trelleborg MV 500P fenders on some outer berths.

Hamnavoe: Burra

Position: 60° 06' N 01° 21' W

Port infrastructure:

Pier, Marina

Main uses and users:

Small fishing and leisure vessels

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Major town services 10 miles by road and two bridges.

Nearby accommodation:

5 miles to The Scalloway Hotel by road and two bridges

Infrastructure constraints:

- Hamnavoe pier is located adjacent to Hamnavoe village, with busy roads and limited turning space.
- Road transport to town services in Lerwick and Scalloway requires crossing of two single-lane bridges (Burra-Trondra and Trondra-Mainland), which may limit heavy traffic use.

Additional information:

-

Walls: West Mainland

Position: 60° 13' N 001° 34' W

Main uses and users:

Port infrastructure:

Pier

Salmon and mussel industry.

Small fishing and leisure vessels.

Small passenger-only ferry service to Foula.

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Water supplies and truck access to Scalloway and Lerwick are available.

Major town services 24 miles by road.

Nearby accommodation:

24 miles to The Shetland Hotel by road

26 miles to Brae Hotel by road

Infrastructure constraints:

-

Additional information:

Laydown area shown may be subject to existing lease agreements, and its inclusion should not be interpreted as its availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

West Burrafirth: West Mainland

Position: 60° 17' N 01° 32' W

Main uses and users:

Small fishing and aquaculture vessels.
Papa Stour ferry service.

Port infrastructure:

RORO ferry terminal, Pier

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Toilets, showers, fresh water, fuel, telephone, waste reception, launching slip, water, stores and truck access to Scalloway and Lerwick.

Major town services 30 miles by road.

Nearby accommodation:

25 miles to The Shetland Hotel by road

27 miles to Brae Hotel by road

28 miles to Busta House Hotel by road

Infrastructure constraints:

Major town services are 25 miles away, partly by thin and winding single-track road, which may limit heavy road traffic

Additional information:

Laydown areas shown may be subject to existing lease agreements, and their inclusion should not be interpreted as their availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Mid Yell: Yell

Position: 60° 36' N 01° 03' W

Main uses and users:

Fishing and aquaculture vessels.

Port infrastructure:

Pier

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Water, stores and ice are available from Cullivoe.

Truck transport by road and ferry to the mainland are available.

Major town services 38 miles by road and ferry.

Nearby accommodation:

19 miles to Sella Ness Camp by road and ferry

24 miles to Brae Hotel by road and ferry

25 miles to Busta House Hotel by road and ferry

Infrastructure constraints:

Access to major town services on the mainland relies on use of the Yell-Mainland ferry, which has a weight limit of 44 tonnes for a full-articulated unit

Additional information:

Laydown area shown may be subject to existing lease agreement, and its inclusion should not be interpreted as its availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Baltasound: Unst

Position: 60° 45' N 00° 50' W

Main uses and users:

Small fishing, aquaculture and leisure vessels.

Port infrastructure:

Pier, Small marina

Temporary outside storage of quarried soapstone.

Facilities and services:

Water, stores, fuel.

Minor welding repairs and net mending facilities.

Truck/ferry access to mainland available.

Major town services 52 miles by road and ferry.

Nearby accommodation:

< 1 mile to Baltasound Hotel by road

35 miles to Sella Ness Camp by road and two ferries

40 miles to Brae Hotel by road and two ferries

41 miles to Busta House Hotel by road and two ferries

Infrastructure constraints:

- Thin single-track road entrance to Baltasound pier, with minimal turning space, may limit capacity for heavy road traffic
- Currently, Baltasound pier is used for the temporary outside storage of quarried soapstone, which may incur competition for laydown space
- Access to major town services on the mainland relies on use of the Yell-Mainland ferry and Unst-Yell ferry, which have weight limits of 44 tonnes for a full-articulated unit

Additional information:

Sheltered by isle of Balta.

Good anchorage for yachts SW of pier.

Laydown area shown may be subject to existing lease agreement, and its inclusion should not be interpreted as its availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Uyeasound: Unst

Position: 60° 41' N 00° 50' W

Main uses and users:

Small fishing, aquaculture and leisure vessels.

Port infrastructure:

Pier, Small marina

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Water, stores, fuel.

Minor welding repairs and net mending facilities.

Truck/ferry access to mainland available.

Major town services 46 miles by road and ferry.

Nearby accommodation:

7 miles to Baltasound Hotel by road

30 miles to Sella Ness Camp by road and two ferries

35 miles to Brae Hotel by road and two ferries

36 miles to Busta House Hotel by road and two ferries

Infrastructure constraints:

- The thin single-track road entrance to Uyeasound pier may limit capacity for heavy road traffic
- Access to major town services on the mainland relies on use of the Yell-Mainland ferry and Unst-Yell ferry, which have weight limits of 44 tonnes for a full-articulated unit

Additional information:

Laydown area shown may be subject to existing lease agreement, and its inclusion should not be interpreted as its availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Hamars Ness: Fetlar

Position: 60° 37' 47" N 00° 55' 52 " W

Main uses and users:

Small fishing, aquaculture and leisure vessels.
Fetlar ferry service

Port infrastructure:

Small pier, RORO ferry terminal

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Stores and fuel.
Water and ice available from Cullivoe and Baltasound.
Truck/ferry access to mainland available.
Major town services 46 miles by road and two ferries.

Nearby accommodation:

There are no hotels or guesthouses on the island of Fetlar.
29 miles to Sella Ness Camp by road and two ferries
34 miles to Brae Hotel by road and two ferries
35 miles to Busta House Hotel by road and two ferries

Infrastructure constraints:

Access to major town services on the mainland relies on use of the Yell-Mainland ferry and Fetlar-Yell ferry, which have weight limits of 44 tonnes for a full-articulated unit

Additional information:

Laydown area shown may be subject to existing lease agreement, and its inclusion should not be interpreted as its availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Symbister: Whalsay

Position: 60° 21' N 01° 02' W

Main uses and users:

Small fishing, aquaculture and leisure vessels.

Port infrastructure:

Modern fendered quayside, Piers, Marina, RORO Ferry Terminal

Regular use by Shetland's pelagic and whitefish fleets (particularly in August).

Whalsay ferry service.

Facilities and services:

Water, ice, stores and fuel from bunker tank.
 Minor welding repairs and net mending facilities.
 Truck/ferry access to mainland available.
 Major town services 28 miles by road and ferry.

Nearby accommodation:

There are no hotels or guesthouses on the island of Whalsay.
 19 miles to Brae Hotel by road and ferry
 20 miles to Busta House Hotel by road and ferry

Infrastructure constraints:

- Symbister is often busy with large fishing vessels, including pelagic and whitefish trawlers, which may create competition for quayside space
- Access to major town services on the mainland relies on use of the Whalsay ferry, which has a weight limit of 44 tonnes for a full-articulated unit

Additional information:

Suitable anchorage in North Voe, sheltered from SW winds.
 Approach is clear and well lit, although North and South entrances have fairly strong currents.
Laydown areas shown may be subject to existing lease agreements, and their inclusion should not be interpreted as availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Out Skerries

Position: 60° 25' N 00° 45' W

Main uses and users:

Small fishing, aquaculture and leisure vessels.
Skerries ferry service.

Port infrastructure:

Pier, RORO ferry terminal, Marina

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Water and stores.
Net mending facilities.
Major town services 40 miles by road and ferry.

Nearby accommodation:

There are no hotels or guesthouses on Out Skerries.
26 miles to Brae Hotel by road and ferry
27 miles to Busta House Hotel by road and ferry

Infrastructure constraints:

Access to major town services on the mainland relies on use of the Out Skerries ferry, which has a weight limit of 34 tonnes for a full-articulated unit

Additional information:

Suitable anchorage in Böd Voe.
Laydown area shown may be subject to existing lease agreement, and its inclusion should not be interpreted as its availability. Availability of areas should be established with the site owners.

Fair Isle

Position: 59° 32' N 01° 36' W

Main uses and users:

Small fishing vessels.

Port infrastructure:

Pier

Fair Isle passenger-only ferry service.

Outside storage:

Facilities and services:

Water and stores.

Major town services 50 miles by road and ferry.

Nearby accommodation:

The Fair Isle Bird Observatory used to provide ample accommodation on the island, but unfortunately burned down in 2019. Otherwise, there are a few guesthouses. Accommodation on the Shetland mainland can be reached by ferry (2 ½ hours) or a short flight.

Infrastructure constraints:

Access to major town services on the mainland relies on use of the Fair Isle ferry, which has no Ro Ro capabilities and takes 2 ½ hours.

No all-weather anchorage.

Additional information:

Summer cruising possible but advice must be sought.

The author of this report was Voar

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